

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL MARKETING AND INFLUENCERS ON CONSUMER PURCHASE DECISIONS IN CAUCAIA/CE

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ABSTRACT

The advancement of digital technologies and the popularization of social networks have transformed marketing strategies and consumer behavior, especially in the context of local businesses. In this scenario, the role of digital influencers stands out as agents capable of impacting purchasing decisions and competitiveness among companies. This article aims to analyze the impact of digital marketing and the role of digital influencers on consumer purchasing decisions in the municipality of Caucaia , Ceará , Brazil. The research adopted a qualitative, descriptive approach, using structured interviews applied to business owners, volunteers, and customers active in the municipality's commercial center as data collection

instruments. Data were collected through digital questionnaires and audio recordings, ensuring greater accuracy in the analysis of information. The results show that digital influencers play a relevant role in sparking the desire to consume, especially when they present products in real-life usage situations, promoting identification and trust on the part of the consumer. The credibility and authenticity of the influencer proved to be determining factors for the success of influencer marketing strategies. Furthermore, it was found that digital marketing has increased consumer bargaining power, making them more informed, critical, and demanding, which poses new challenges for local businesses. The research also revealed the potential of digital marketing as a tool to encourage conscious consumption and customer loyalty. It is that digital marketing and influencer marketing are fundamental strategic tools for strengthening the competitiveness and sustainability of local businesses in Caucaia -CE, provided they are used in a planned, ethical manner and aligned with the expectations of the target audience.

Keywords: Digital marketing. Influencers. Strategies. Opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

With technological advancements, both in electronic devices and social media, communication has become broader, faster, and more accessible, directly impacting how companies and organizations promote their products and services.

With all the freedom and ease afforded by the internet, content is becoming one of the main tools used by brands in their digital marketing planning. In this scenario, some individuals have stood out on certain social networks, gathering and influencing thousands – in some cases, millions – of people: these are the digital influencers.

Given this scenario, the number of digital consumers has increased significantly, since a large portion of the population spends a lot of time on social media, consuming varied content, the so-called "niches," each with its respective influencers, whether in the areas of cosmetics, automobiles, food, health, among others.

DataReportal platform, which provides information about the global digital environment through data analysis, recently published the study "Digital 2024: Brazil," with data on the largest social media platforms used in Brazil. According to the research, 76.6% of the total Brazilian *internet user base* (regardless of age) uses at least one of these platforms. In total, 55.6% of users are women, while 44.4% are men.

These data reflect the widespread adoption of social media throughout the country, which is also evident locally. In Caucaia, several examples of the use of tools and strategies in marketing can be observed. Digital technology is used in business ventures, organizational environments, and individual professional profiles.

Given this context, the following question arises: **how have digital marketing and the use of influencers impacted sales and competition among companies in Caucaia?**

Given this question, this article aims to analyze the impact of digital marketing and the role of influencers on consumer purchasing decisions in Caucaia, Ceará, Brazil. Its specific objectives are: a) to evaluate the influence of digital marketing on the quality of sales in Caucaia; b) to understand the satisfaction of consumers and businesses with the use of digital influencers; c) to identify how digital marketing has contributed to expanding the reach and mobility of local businesses.

This research is justified by the growing importance of digital marketing and the role of digital influencers in contemporary consumer behavior, especially in a context marked by the intense use of social media. Technological advancements and the popularization of these platforms have transformed the way companies interact with their audiences, creating new opportunities and challenges for local businesses.

The choice of theme arose from daily observations surrounding social media and the emergence of numerous influencers, given their significant impact on sales. Its relevance to the field of Administration is justified by the importance and necessity of discussing it with a focus on generating information for the business community of the municipality of Caucaia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Marketing: Concepts and Strategies

There are several definitions of marketing, some more complex than others, and some with more specific focuses than others. However, Kotler's succinct definition... (1996, p. 31), presents the essence of marketing in a simple and complete way: "Marketing is the human activity directed at satisfying needs and wants through exchange." In a current context, using technology, we have digital marketing, which is defined as that which uses strategies with some digital component in the marketing mix: product, price, place, or promotion.

The use of digital strategies in marketing and communication campaigns by companies has diversified through the systematic use of tools such as the integration of mobile and portable web access and the optimization of search engines, establishing new pillars of integrated communication. The pursuit of improved performance and positioning of organizations grows as "digital presence" assumes strategic importance for achieving better visibility among specific audiences on a recurring basis.

MacKenna (2006) presents the convergence between marketing and technology, stating that technology transforms markets and integrates knowledge into the strategies that guide activities. According to Telles (2010), social media is included within the scope of digital marketing, which encompasses *Search Engine Marketing (SEM)* strategies with sponsored links in search engines and *Search Engine... Optimization (SEO)* with website optimization to improve search engine ranking, along with *mobile marketing actions*, email marketing, online press relations, modern websites and microsites, designed according to Web 2.0 and 3.0 concepts.

SEM refers to the process of using web search engines to promote a particular website, increasing its traffic and loyalty. It involves internal actions (online) (page) and external actions (off-page). *On-page actions Page optimization strategies are called SEO and encompass techniques for manipulating the content and structure of website pages. Off-page optimization actions refer to strategies carried out outside the website and range from public relations actions to sponsored links (Gabriel, 2009).*

Ricotta (2010), SEO encompasses techniques and methods aimed at improving the ranking of pages in search engines. In other words, when a user types a keyword into a search engine, the goal of SEO is to ensure that one or more pages of a website appear among the top organic search results. SEO actions include clear URLs, adherence to web standards, rational page titles, and the correct use of tags. HTML, which is the language used to build web pages, is the optimization of a page or an entire website. This page ranking depends, therefore, on relevance, which is defined by algorithms that consist of a set of programming instructions to calculate and define how important a page is" (Teixeira, 2008, p. 79).

Digital Influencers and Their Role in Consumer Behavior

According to Porto (2010), an individual is not necessarily capable of accurately evaluating all of their decision-making. Some everyday situations can end up influencing the choice process, such as: not having access to sufficient information about the product, overvaluing available information, being under pressure at some point, or even losing focus due to having too many options.

Therefore, marketing actions become a major influencer in purchasing decisions. It is common for consumers not to base their choices solely on their physiological needs. Organizations have begun to realize that, in order to influence consumers' purchasing decisions,

they must create forms of advertising that capture attention and somehow create value for them (Ikeda; Veludo-de-Oliveira , 2004).

When a brand connects with consumers through social media, publishing information and monitoring its presence, people tend to have a better image of it (Perez, Gosling; Andrade, 2014). Another factor that influences consumer choice is the offering of free gifts, online advertising videos, and the use of children's characters or celebrities (Andrade; Azevedo, 2014; Santos; Batalha, 2010).

According to a study published in Exame magazine (2018), 77% of consumers make purchasing decisions based on social media. It was also published that the main activities Brazilians perform through social media are: discovering brands (43%), *feedback* and recommendations about a brand (43%), and following favorite brands (39%).

Then comes the digital influencer, who is an opinion leader capable of directly influencing consumer opinions, tastes, and purchases. Through exposure on digital networks, they stand out and reach a large number of people who begin to follow content published on their profile, or through promotions by third-party brands, showcasing their daily lives, experiences, lifestyle, and opinions on a given subject.

The posts follow a daily frequency, showcasing various products, brands, recommendations, and usage tips. In this way, they influence the audience, causing a visible and proven impact, and with this repercussion, they gain enough strength to transform and shape opinions in specific niches. Unlike television advertising, for example, the influencer presents the brand by applying their own experience, using their authenticity and creativity, so that it doesn't seem forced.

Impacts of Digital Marketing and Influencers on Sales and Business Competitiveness

Considered opinion leaders and content creators, they attract the attention of traditional media, which does not cease to exist, but must jointly share space with these new models and levels of participation. Virtual means of dissemination such as blogs, YouTube channels, Instagram profiles, Twitter accounts (X), initially created as hobbies, are now autonomous media with influence in the market.

Winning over audiences through proximity and perceived intimacy, influencers gain notoriety on specific topics, establishing credibility to recommend products and services (Camargo; Estevanim ; Silveira, 2017). Exploring this new trend, the influencer market is increasingly taking up space in the media and, especially, in consumers' purchasing decision-

making process. A key differentiator is that, in addition to producing new content based on what their followers expect, it's possible to build a close relationship and thus convey the credibility that truly inspires influence.

To broaden understanding from a business perspective, the results of the "ROI & Influencer Marketing 2019" survey show that 68% of participating companies consider Influencer Marketing an essential strategy for their businesses, while 69% affirm that this communication format generates distinct and more effective results than other types of media. Compared to the first edition of the survey, conducted in 2017, a significant increase is observed: in that year, 36% of companies invested up to R\$ 100,000 annually; in 2019, 40% declared an intention to invest between R\$ 100,000 and R\$ 700,000 in Influencer Marketing actions.

The research also reveals that brands recognize the good return and intend to invest even more than in the previous year. The research was conducted between February 18th and 22nd, 2019, with 94 large Brazilian companies. More than 60% of the responses came from high-level executives, such as directors, managers, and coordinators from companies in different segments: consumer goods, telecommunications and media, automotive, financial services, retail, technology, and services (Kohn, 2019). Investing in this type of strategy has become a trend nowadays, due to the very positive results for companies, the possibility of segmenting actions, and the moderate investment cost.

The possibility of organizations contacting influencers directly also greatly facilitates this market, since the old model of allocating a large advertising budget to advertising agencies is no longer fundamentally necessary. Another relevant point is the diverse ways in which influencer professionals work and price their services, thus giving companies the opportunity to find what best fits their budget and needs.

the internet and social media have enabled greater interaction and exchange of information with consumers or readers. Therefore, the internet is capable of providing greater consumer participation in brand building through their opinions and discussions on the topics at hand (Cunha; Cunha & Monte, 2015).

Marketing is constantly evolving, transforming itself in line with market changes, globalization, and the advancement of the internet. This dynamism demands that companies constantly update their strategies in order to keep up with trends and maintain their competitiveness in an increasingly competitive environment (Kotler, 2021).

The increased accessibility and profitability prospects that investments in these strategies provide to companies have made *marketing* an increasingly present sector in

businesses, being considered extremely important to bring visibility and advantages over the competition, as well as being an option for both large companies and micro and small companies (Cerqueira, 2020).

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This study employs an approach that encompasses both qualitative and descriptive aspects. The research is descriptive in nature. According to Gil (2010), descriptive research is characterized by the use of standardized data collection techniques, such as surveys and systematic observations, allowing the researcher to describe phenomena, record facts, and analyze the application of known models and techniques in different contexts. Therefore, this study adopts a descriptive design to detail the phenomena related to digital marketing and the role of influencers in purchasing decisions in the municipality of Caucaia.

The interviews were conducted with selected subjects, including business owners, volunteers, and clients, all residents and active in the center of Caucaia – CE, where data collection took place during the period of December 9, 2025.

For data collection, a structured questionnaire instrument was used, applied in the field (APPENDIX A), through digital platforms such as *Google Forms*, in addition to audio recordings using recorders, ensuring the accurate capture of the information collected.

The theoretical and practical foundation of this research was based on primary sources, including books, academic articles, specialized journals, websites, and other materials relevant to the topic addressed.

Regarding the participation criteria, only those subjects who met the previously established requirements, such as business owners, volunteers, and clients, were included. All individuals who did not meet these criteria were automatically excluded from the research.

This study addresses a topic of public knowledge and was conducted respecting all current ethical standards, including preserving the confidentiality of personal information, the anonymity of participants, and ensuring that no subject is placed in an embarrassing situation.

The research will benefit the local businesses involved by enabling a better understanding of the use of Digital Marketing tools, contributing to improved visibility and results.

The Informed Consent Form was delivered to and signed by the interviewees, ensuring voluntary and conscious participation. Participants were duly informed about the possibility of

withdrawing at any time and the right not to answer certain questions, guaranteeing total autonomy throughout the entire process.

RESULTS

This section presents and discusses the results obtained from interviews conducted with business owners from different commercial segments in the municipality of Caucaia–CE, including clothing, electronics, and accessories stores. The qualitative research allowed us to understand, from the perspective of the merchants themselves, how digital marketing and the actions of digital influencers impact consumer purchasing decisions, negotiation dynamics, and the performance of local businesses.

Digital influencers and the awakening of consumer desire.

The results show that digital influencers play an important role in shaping the desire to consume among their followers. According to those interviewed, the main strategy used by influencers is to present products in real-life usage situations, integrated into daily life, which facilitates consumer identification with the advertised item. This practice was mentioned in all segments analyzed, whether through demonstrating clothes on the body, using accessories in *outfit composition* , or conducting practical tests of electronic products.

Business owners reported that this type of content fosters a closer relationship between brand and consumer, as it allows the audience to imagine themselves using the product. Furthermore, it highlights the creation of social proof, where the influencer's positive experience acts as an incentive for making a purchase decision.

Thus, it can be observed that, in Caucaia-CE, digital influencers fulfill a strategic function by reducing consumer uncertainty and accelerating the decision-making process.

The influencer's credibility and consumer trust.

Another relevant finding concerns the importance of the digital influencer's credibility. Unanimously, respondents stated that the trust conveyed by the influencer is crucial for the success of digital marketing campaigns. When the influencer demonstrates consistency between their lifestyle, opinions, and the products they promote, there is a transfer of credibility to the advertised brand.

On the other hand, business leaders also highlighted that influencers considered unreliable or overly commercial tend to generate distrust, negatively impacting sales. This aspect was especially emphasized in the electronics segment, where consumers seek technical information and honest reviews before making a purchase.

The discussion of these results highlights that credibility is an essential intangible asset in influencer marketing. Authenticity, transparency, and alignment with brand values proved to be decisive factors for the satisfaction of both entrepreneurs and consumers, fulfilling the specific objective of understanding the stakeholders' perception of the use of digital influencers.

The bargaining power of the consumer in the digital age.

The data collected indicates that digital media has increased consumer bargaining power. According to those interviewed, customers arrive at physical and online stores more informed, having previously researched prices, reviews, and available alternatives on the market. This behavior alters the traditional relationship between seller and buyer, demanding greater flexibility and transparency from businesses.

Online price comparisons and customer reviews have been identified as factors that directly influence negotiation. When customers find lower prices on other platforms, they tend to request discounts or additional benefits. Similarly, negative reviews generate questions and insecurity, while positive reviews increase confidence and facilitate the completion of the sale.

These results reinforce the idea that digital marketing expands access to information and empowers the consumer, making them more critical and demanding. For local businesses in Caucaia-CE, this represents the challenge of competing on price and quality, customer service, and perceived differentiators.

Digital marketing and promoting conscious consumption.

A significant finding of the research was the recognition by business owners that digital media can encourage more conscious consumption practices. Respondents reported that by disseminating clear information about durability, quality, environmental impact, and proper ways to use products, consumers demonstrate greater responsibility in their choices.

In the fashion and accessories segments, for example, the appreciation for content that teaches how to combine pieces in different ways, reducing impulsive purchases, stood out. In

the electronics segment, awareness of the real need for the product and its lifespan was identified as a factor contributing to more rational decisions.

These results demonstrate that digital marketing can play an educational role, aligning itself with more sustainable practices and strengthening long-term relationships between consumers and businesses. Although this type of approach may reduce immediate impulse sales, business owners reported increased customer loyalty and trust.

The future of digital media and the role of new technologies.

Regarding future prospects, respondents agreed that digital media is moving towards a greater emphasis on authenticity and segmentation. Smaller, yet highly niche influencers were identified as more effective than major celebrities, especially for local businesses.

Furthermore, new technologies, particularly artificial intelligence, were recognized as strategic tools in digital marketing. Business owners reported that AI has contributed to automating customer service, personalizing offers, analyzing consumer behavior, and optimizing inventory management and advertising campaigns.

The adoption of these technologies can broaden the reach and competitiveness of local businesses in Caucaia-CE, directly addressing the specific objective of identifying how digital marketing contributes to the mobility and expansion of companies.

Challenges and opportunities of influencer marketing for local businesses

Finally, the results reveal that influencer marketing presents significant challenges and opportunities. Among the main challenges are choosing influencers aligned with the brand identity, measuring the return on investment, and the risk of association with potential controversies involving public figures.

Conversely, the opportunities include rapidly increasing visibility, creating an emotional connection with the audience, humanizing the brand, and conquering new market niches. When well-planned, influencer marketing has proven to be an effective strategy for strengthening digital presence and boosting sales for local businesses.

Overall, the results of this research confirm that digital marketing and the influence of consumers have a significant impact on their purchasing decisions in Caucaia-CE, contributing to the transformation of commercial practices and the strengthening of local commerce.

DISCUSSION

The results of this research show that digital marketing and the actions of digital influencers have a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions in Caucaia-CE, corroborating studies that point to the centrality of digital media in contemporary consumer behavior. It was observed that the presentation of products in real-life usage situations, carried out by influencers, generates greater identification from the public, reduces the perception of risk, and accelerates the purchase decision-making process. This finding is consistent with Kotler, Kartajaya, and Setiawan (2017), who highlight that trust and emotional proximity are essential elements in current marketing.

The credibility of the influencer has emerged as a determining factor for the effectiveness of influencer marketing strategies. Business reports indicate that influencers perceived as authentic and consistent with the products they promote generate greater trust and, consequently, better commercial results. This aspect confirms the arguments of Brown and Hayes (2008), who argue that authenticity is a fundamental condition for the success of influencer marketing, since consumers tend to reject excessively commercial communications. Furthermore, according to Kotler and Keller (2018), the trust transferred from the influencer to the brand strengthens the perceived value of the product, especially in digital environments.

Another relevant point identified was the increase in consumer bargaining power provided by digital media. Easier access to information, such as price comparisons and online reviews, has made consumers more informed, critical, and demanding. This result aligns with Solomon's (2016) reflections, who points out that increased access to information alters the relationship between companies and consumers, shifting bargaining power to the customer. In this context, local entrepreneurs in Caucaia-CE face the challenge of competing on price and on differentiators such as customer service, experience, and digital reputation.

The research also revealed that digital marketing can act as a tool to encourage conscious consumption. By providing clear information about the quality, durability, and proper use of products, companies contribute to more responsible choices on the part of consumers. This finding aligns with the studies of Peattie and Belz (2010), who advocate for marketing oriented towards stimulating consumption and promoting more conscious and sustainable decisions. Although this practice may reduce impulse purchases, respondents reported greater customer loyalty and strengthened customer relationships.

Regarding future prospects, the results indicate a trend towards valuing authenticity and segmentation in digital marketing. Smaller, but more niche influencers were identified as more

effective, especially for local businesses, reinforcing the idea of more personalized and closer communication with the consumer. Furthermore, the use of technologies such as artificial intelligence proved relevant for process optimization, offer personalization, and analysis of purchasing behavior, in line with the Marketing 5.0 concept presented by Kotler, Kartajaya , and Setiawan (2021).

Overall, the discussion of the results confirms that digital marketing and influencer marketing represent fundamental strategic tools for expanding the reach, competitiveness, and sustainability of local businesses in Caucaia-CE. When used in a planned, ethical manner, and aligned with consumer expectations, these resources contribute to increased sales, the building of lasting relationships, and the strengthening of local commerce.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study aimed to analyze the impact of digital marketing and the role of digital influencers on consumer purchasing decisions in the municipality of Caucaia, Ceará, Brazil. Using a qualitative approach, it was possible to understand, from the perspective of local business owners, how digital media is transforming commercial practices and the relationship between companies and consumers.

The results showed that digital influencers play a significant role in sparking consumer desire, especially when they use authentic content and demonstrate products in real-life usage situations. The influencer's credibility proved crucial for consumer trust and sales performance, reinforcing the importance of alignment between brand, influencer, and target audience. Furthermore, it was found that digital media has increased consumer bargaining power, making them more informed, critical, and demanding, which requires greater transparency and competitive differentiation from companies.

Another relevant aspect concerns the potential of digital marketing to encourage more conscious consumption practices, through the dissemination of clear information about the quality, durability, and proper use of products. It was also observed that new technologies, such as artificial intelligence, have contributed to the optimization of marketing processes, expanding the reach and efficiency of local businesses.

It is concluded that digital marketing and influencer marketing are fundamental strategic tools for strengthening local commerce in Caucaia-CE. However, their effectiveness depends on planning, authenticity, and the ethical use of digital strategies. A limitation is the small

number of participants; therefore, future research suggests expanding the sample size and including the perspective of consumers to deepen the understanding of the topic.

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